

How explainable is explainability? Towards better metrics for explainable AI

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Abstract. Despite the fact that machine learning has been applied in innumerable domains, its models have usually operated in a black box fashion, i.e. without revealing the rationale behind their decisions. For human users, insufficient model transparency may result in the lack of trust in the technology, effectively hindering its development and adoption. This pressing need for the society to understand the reasoning for the model's decisions gave rise to the concept of explainable AI (xAI), which has been the subject of extensive research. Since its introduction, a number of techniques providing explainability have been proposed. Yet, there has been no consensus reached regarding how to measure and evaluate the performance of the explainability methods. So far, the state-of-the-art literature has proposed two directions for evaluating explainable AI – the technical one and the human-centered one. Although the literature deems the technical way to be the objective one, it still suggests supplementing the evaluation with the subjective, human-centered approach, which proves to be time-consuming and requires considerable effort. This paper highlights the need to enhance and improve the existing technical metrics, to quantify the explainability of ML models in an objective, automated and time and cost-effective way. The text presents the current state-of-the-art in xAI evaluation metrics, discussing both human-centered and computer-centered approaches. Its contribution is in its comprehensive discussion of the evaluation methods for explainable AI (xAI).

Keywords: artificial intelligence · AI · explainability · explainable AI · xAI · machine learning · ML

1 Introduction

In the past few years, the domain of artificial intelligence (AI) has made considerable breakthroughs, with many applications being built and implemented in a variety of sectors, including decision-making [1], computer vision [2], business [3], cybersecurity [4] and natural language processing (NLP) [5]. However, as AI systems become more widely used and deployed, there is a rising worry

about their lack of transparency and explainability. Best-performing AI technologies, such as deep learning, usually work in a "black box" manner, and are challenging to comprehend and interpret [6]. This is so, as these approaches rely on massive neural networks trained on huge datasets with a wide variety of parameters; therefore, they are capable of learning and making judgments in ways that humans cannot understand [7]. This issue becomes all the more crucial in high-stakes fields such as self-driving cars [8], banking [6] or healthcare [9], where AI systems' decisions might have serious implications. In order to address this problem, the discipline called Explainable AI (xAI) has evolved, with the goal of designing AI systems that can offer clear and intelligible explanations for their choices and decisions [10].

In fact, xAI is more than a subfield of computer science or machine learning; it is a multidisciplinary area that incorporates techniques and concepts from artificial intelligence, human-computer interaction, as well as psychology or philosophy [11]. It is a dynamically expanding subject, with many scientists, universities, and business companies attempting to create new xAI methods and applications.

Explainability is critical for AI systems for a variety of reasons. Firstly, it increases user and stakeholder trust and confidence in the system since they can see how the system makes judgments. It also allows the identification and fixing of algorithm errors and biases, as the system's explanations may be utilized to identify and get rid of any faults. Finally, explainability can help in the creation and enhancement of AI systems by increasing knowledge of the fundamental mechanisms as well as decision-making processes [12].

There are various techniques to xAI, each having its own set of advantages and disadvantages, such as the human-in-the-loop explanations, model interpretability, post-hoc explanations, surrogate explanations, etc. [13][14]. Human-in-the-loop explanations include people actively participating in the decision-making process, delivering explanations suited to the user's individual context and requirements [15]. Model interpretability approaches seek to make the model's internal workings more visible and intelligible [6]. Post-hoc explanations give explanations after a choice has been made [16]. Surrogate explanations involve training intrinsically explainable models to help explain the decisions of more accurate, opaque models.

With the development of xAI methods, there arose the need of evaluating whether explainability is, in fact, explainable. So far, no agreement has been reached by the scientific community concerning how to quantify and measure the quality of explanations, and what metrics should be taken into consideration. Nevertheless, in the past few years, a variety of metrics for analyzing xAI models have been proposed.

They can roughly be divided into two types: human-centered [17] and computer-centered (technical) ones [18]. This paper discusses the current state-of-the-art xAI evaluation metrics, reviewing the numerous measures that have been suggested as well as their merits and limitations, and signalling the complexity of this matter. Its main goal is to emphasize the urgent need of coming up with

an objective solution, combining the advantages of both approaches, so that artificial intelligence is never a black box again.

2 Evaluating xAI

Evaluation of explainability must begin by defining explainability as such. One of the proposed definitions describes explainability as composed of two elements, interpretability and fidelity. Interpretability refers to the explanation being understandable for humans and is composed of two elements as well, namely clarity and parsimony. On the other hand, fidelity (the components of which being completeness and soundness) is achieved when the task model has been accurately described [19].

Though well-defined as far as the needs are concerned, evaluating explainability has been deemed one of the most pressing challenges for machine learning. As Molnar et al. explain this, it is related to the fact that the ground truth is unknown (unlike in the case of evaluating predictive performance, for example), and no straightforward tool exists which is able to quantify interpretability or correctness of an explanation [20]. Evaluating xAI-generated explanations is also a compound task, as it is related both to the applied technical approach and the needs of end-users at the same time. Lastly, evaluating explanations is so complex due to the research of xAI evaluation being multidisciplinary, stemming from a multitude of knowledge domains [21].

According to Markus et al., there are two main goals of evaluating xAI:

- To check whether an application achieves explainability, i.e., if the explanations fulfill the defined objectives of explainability, and
- To make a comparison between explanation methods and decide upon the most preferred one [19].

On the other hand, Zhou et al. define evaluating the quality of an explanation by checking to which level the attributes of explainability are satisfied; these properties being interpretability, which consists in clarity, parsimony, and broadness, and fidelity, understood as a combination of completeness and soundness [22].

There have been proposed several taxonomies of xAI evaluation methods. So far, a scientific consensus has not been reached so as to establish one, universal taxonomy. The two ways of evaluating interpretations proposed by Molnar et al. are the human-centered evaluation, involving the studies with humans, either experts or laypeople, and the mathematically quantifiable metrics, which the authors call objective evaluations [20].

The three groups that Doshi-Velez and Kim have proposed for dividing the evaluation approaches into are application-grounded, human-grounded as well as functionality-grounded. The application-grounded evaluation consists in performing experiments with the help of end-users, whilst the human-grounded approach relies on lay humans. On the other hand, the functionality-grounded

evaluation methods derive proxies from the formal definition of interpretability [23]. Experiments with human participants let one apply qualitative as well as quantitative metrics, the former assessing how useful the explanations are if users are satisfied with them and if they can trust those explanations. In turn, the quantitative metrics assess task performance (its accuracy), response time, etc. [20] The methods belonging to the first two groups are deemed not as objective as the ones belonging to the third one, this being caused by the fact that the choice of the specific group of human participants directly influences the final results of the evaluation.

Similarly, Zhou et al. apply the same taxonomy as Doshi-Velez and Kim, but they group the application-grounded and human-grounded evaluation into one category – human-centered evaluations. They also remark that with the human-centered explanations, it is possible to apply both quantitative and qualitative metrics [22].

All things considered, the most general way of organizing the methods seems to be the division into the human-centered and the computer-centered ones, as suggested by Lopes et al.[21].

3 The two approaches to evaluating Explainable AI

This section discusses in greater detail the human-centered and technical methods of evaluating xAI, their main elements, tools and techniques applied as part of them as well as their advantages and disadvantages; the section closes with the comparison of both methods as far as their pros and cons are concerned.

3.1 Human-centred explanation evaluation methods

The main goals of the human-centered ways of evaluating the quality of an explanation are to assess the way the decision-making process of an AI model is explained to humans, and how humans perceive the explanations and justifications provided by the model. It is also crucial for making sure a system is suited for its target users, i.e., for their values, beliefs and expectations, and meets their needs and expectations. Although scientists tend to agree about this general principle, the specific sets of constructs and elements that should be evaluated varies from paper to paper.

Amongst the concepts which are mentioned the most often there are transparency – in this context, referring to the level to which the explanations can be understood by people, and if they meet their expectations, and fairness, i.e., checking whether the explanations are bias-free. Then, there are the issues of accountability, relating to the question whether the system is accountable for its decisions, and whether the explanations can be defended to human users and interpretability - that is being understandable for humans. The latter aspect is related to understandability, which is the aspect of explanation which refers to checking if an explanation is comprehensive, clear, and concise enough to be understood by an average user. According to [21], this category may be further

divided into user’s perceived understandability, as well as user’s predictions of model output and model failure.

Further, there is the concept of trustworthiness; it relates to the question if the explanations align with the users’ expectations, if the users perceive these explanations to be credible and if the output of a system can be believed in without any doubt or fear. It also relates to how comfortably a user applies the system to tasks and how much confidence they have. Similarly the concept of usefulness means that the explanations are helpful to humans in understanding the decisions of a system, or it contributes to improving the system. Lastly, there is performance; in this context, not only referring to the models, but to their users as well [21].

On top of that, explanations have to be ethical [24], i.e., not violate human privacy, autonomy, dignity, etc. Lastly, it is important for the xAI system to be user-centred – in the context of explanations, it means they are suitable for the target audience.

The evaluation based on human assessment may be performed in a variety of ways, and achieved with a number of different tools and methods, like surveys, user studies and interviews, all of them aimed at collecting user feedback concerning the usability, understandability and trustworthiness of a model. Typically, in such studies, human participants first interact with a system and then assess its explanations, checking for understandability, trustworthiness, and usefulness.

For example, a number of human evaluators may be tasked with assessing the quality of an explanation, by means of crowdsourcing. Conversely, instead of a random group of people, this kind of assessment may be performed by a group of experts in the field.

One of the other approaches focuses on how effectively the explanation helps people make better decisions. This can be measured in the course of user studies. In such a case, a participant is asked to make decisions based on the predictions given by an AI model, as well as the accompanying explanations behind its results. The effectiveness is assessed depending on what the quality of the decision was [25].

Some other specific tools and methods used for the task of evaluating explanations include the think-aloud method, user self-explanation, qualitative interview, 5-, 7- or even 10-point Likert-scale questionnaires, System Usability Scale (SUS) questionnaires, post-study questionnaires, diary studies [21], mental models, task duration and cognitive load, simulated experiments, etc. [26].

3.2 Computer-centred explanation evaluation methods

If one follows the taxonomy proposed by Lopes et al., there is a distinct division of the computer-centered explanation evaluation methods, namely into the ones that concentrate on the property of interpretability (if and how humans can understand the explanation) and the one focusing on fidelity (if a model is explained in a way which is accurate). The former may then be divided into the properties of broadness, simplicity/parsimony and clarity, and the latter – into soundness

and completeness [21]. As the authors remark, without human assessment, it is substantially more challenging to measure interpretability than fidelity, owing to the subjective nature of the question of what makes an explanation understandable. In addition to these two categories, other computer-centered properties have been proposed as well, such as identity, stability, separability, etc.

As Nauta et al. argue, explainability is no binary characteristic. This means that it should be assessed by checking the degree to which the relevant properties are satisfied [27]. Thus, besides performance metrics, the technical evaluation of xAI involves assessing the quality of explanation, checking for relevance, consistency, etc. [28]. The categories proposed by Belaid et al. are fidelity, fragility, stability, simplicity, stress and others [29]. In turn, Rosenfeld has developed their own set of metrics for evaluating xAI explanation, called D,R,F and S. D means the performance difference between the agent’s model and the performance of the logic presented as an explanation. R represents how many rules the agent’s explanation contains. F stands for how many features the explanation consists in. Lastly, S describes how stable the explanation is [30][31]. Finally, Nauta et al. have proposed the following list of 12 properties of explanation assessment, called “Co-12”. They encompass: Correctness, Completeness, Consistency, Continuity, Contrastivity, Covariate complexity, Compactness, Compositionality, Confidence, Context Coherence, and Controllability [27].

Therefore, there is no scientific consensus concerning this topic as well. Still, the ultimate choice of metrics is dependent on the domain in which the model is applied, or even on the specific tasks of the model.

Some of the most noteworthy of the proposed methods of computer-centered, technical ways of evaluating the explanations provided by xAI models which have been proposed in the subject literature include:

- creating saliency maps, which reflect how important various features or inputs are to the model’s decision, and then using methods like the one based on randomization tests proposed by Adebayo et al. [32]
- ablation testing, i.e. retraining the model whilst removing certain features/inputs, in order to determine how important they are to the model’s decision, for example the RemOve And Retrain approach (ROAR) [33]
- attribution methods, e.g. the Taylor attribution network [34]
- measuring the depth of a decision tree [35]

Another list of the specific computer-centred methods for assessing explanations has been gathered by Nauta et al. and encompasses such techniques as Model Parameter Randomization Check, Explanation Randomization Check, White Box Check, Controlled Synthetic Data Check, Single Deletion, Incremental Deletion (or Incremental Addition), Preservation Check, Deletion Check, Fidelity, Predictive Performance, Implementation Invariance, Stability for Slight Variations, Fidelity for Slight Variations, Connectedness, Target Sensitivity, Target Discriminateness, Data Randomization Check, Covariate Homogeneity, Covariate Regularity, Size, Redundancy, Counterfactual Compactness, Perceptual Realism, Confidence Accuracy, Pragmatism, Simulated User Study, Alignment with Domain Knowledge, XAI Methods’ Agreement [27].

3.3 Human-centered vs. computer-centered evaluation

The xAI evaluation methods belonging to each of the approaches have their specific pros and cons.

The human-centred evaluation is able to provide subtle cues and details that the other approach is not able to uncover. It is also said that the evidence of success it provides is the strongest [22] and that its impact is real-world [23]. Yet, these methods do not necessarily scale well, so they may be inefficient, too time and resource-consuming and generally daunting [22] [30]. On top of that, they may not be objective, or they might even be biased [30]. In addition, this type of evaluation lacks the ability to clearly measure how the model performs in a general way [21]. Lastly, there are a number of reasons why this kind of evaluation may be unethical, e.g., when the evaluators of crowd platforms the study bases on are not adequately compensated, or the platforms themselves are not properly regulated [27].

By contrast, the computer-centred approach to evaluation is called the objective one. It allows getting insight into the model’s performance and interpretability. As the machine-powered studies “vastly outpace” human studies [27], they help save money, time and other resources, they are also extremely useful at the lower levels of model’s maturity, as there is no need to organize a group of participants to test it yet. Lastly, they do not come with the ethical issues of the other group. However, this approach lacks the insight of end-users; this makes it more difficult to tailor the model to the users’ needs and expectations.

The pros and cons of both approaches have been summarized in Table 1.

Table 1. The advantages and disadvantages of the human-centred and computer-centred approaches to xAI evaluation.

xAI evaluation approach	Advantages	Disadvantages
human-centred	“the strongest evidence of success [22]” provides valuable information on the specific users’ perspective “real world impact” [23]	expensive time-consuming subjective may be inefficient [22] may be biased not very scalable [30] may be unethical [27][23]
computer-centered	gives insight into the performance and interpretability saves time saves money “vastly outpaces” human studies [27] no ethical issues useful at the lower levels of the method’s maturity [23]	does not take user perspective into account

4 Towards improved metrics

As already mentioned, experts in the field have proposed a number of ways, methods and approaches to evaluating the explanations provided by the xAI models, centered either around human users, or the technology itself. In the recent years, there has been a heated discussion, on both the need of coming up with the metrics and the suggestions on what they should measure, and how.

Yet, there is still no universal solution which seamlessly combines the two approaches, i.e., is objective, whilst providing the detailed human insight, preferably in an automated way of assessing. Although the human-centred approaches provide reflection and nuances that the technical ones are not able to deliver, the evaluation methods involving humans are not very time and cost-effective. One might say that at the moment, one approach complements the other.

In the course of the study by Nauta et al., who took a closer look into how scientists evaluate the explanations of AI models, it turned out that one third of studies were based on anecdotal evidence only. About one-fifth evaluated models with human subjects in a user study, fewer than a quarter of which employed domain experts. Only about half of the experiments applied quantitative evaluation [27]. This means that a significant progress has been observed, as the studies by Adadi and Berrada [36] and Nunes and Jannach [37] indicated that just about half a decade ago very few papers evaluated the presented xAI models in any meaningful way (5% and 21%, respectively) [27]. There is still plenty of room for improvement, though.

All in all, there exist a number of approaches for xAI evaluation. Although the final choice of tools and methods may be dependent on the task or the target audience, xAI developers and scientists should always strive for providing explanations which are as objective as possible, but ideally, include some form of human-centered evaluation of explanations, too. In addition to this, with the ongoing technological development, efforts should be undertaken to improve and enhance the existing metrics, to better reflect the state-of-the-art. The path to achieving these objectives can only begin once a more general agreement has been reached within the scientific community concerning the exact metrics and properties to measure.

5 Conclusions

This work has summarized the discussion on the complicated, complex subject of measuring the quality of explainable artificial intelligence (xAI) explanations. Although there is no scientific consensus concerning the taxonomy of the evaluation methods, nor what exactly should be measured and how, the members of the scientific community see eye to eye about the necessity of evaluating the explanations provided by algorithms, at every stage of the model's development.

As the analyses of the scientific literature have shown, at this moment, it seems that an assessment method should, ideally, provide the advantages of computer-centered evaluation methods, but always keep humans in mind.

Acknowledgement

This research is funded under the Horizon Europe ULTIMATE Project, which has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under grant agreement No. 101070162.

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